

Effects of sylvopastoral treatments on cork-oaks (*Quercus suber* L.) mineral nutrition and growth.*

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SUMMARY

A three year long study has been undertaken in eight cork-oak forest sites located in three Mediterranean regions, two in Catalonia (South of France and North - East of Spain) and one in Sardinia (Italy), submitted to sylvopastoral treatments in order to protect them from fires and for the revival of cork exploitation. The aim of this work is to assess the effects of the thinning, the shrub clearing, the sowing of leguminous plants and grazing on the mineral nutrition and the growth of the cork-oaks and the study of the features of their mineral nutrition. The longitudinal growth was increased by the treatments but the radial growth was not. Soil mineral composition was not significantly improved, but a trend towards higher N and P contents in the treated plots was observed. The increase of the N and P foliar contents in the treated plots suggests an improvement of the N and P nutrition of the trees, resulting from the suppression of the competition for the nutrients available in the soil, the enrichment in N of the soil by the leguminous plant, and the reduction of the turn-over time of the organic matter by the grazing. On the Catalan sites, the longitudinal growth was positively correlated to the pH and to the Ca, N, P, and K soil contents as well as being negatively correlated to the Mn leaf contents.

Key words : Evergreen tree, foliar analysis, forest management, mineral nutrients, *Trifolium subterraneum* L..

* : Submitted to the "Journal of Applied Ecology" .

INTRODUCTION

For several years, the North-Mediterranean cork-oak forests, which are mainly private forests have been neglected. So, they are becoming more and more sensitive to fire and less and less productive. The general will for cork-oak forest renewal and for the increase of cork production, has led to several management programmes in order to reduce fire risks and to make bark stripping easier. A three year long study has been undertaken in eight cork-oak forest sites, located in three Mediterranean regions, two in Catalonia (South of France and North - East of Spain) and one in Sardinia (Italy), and submitted to sylvopastoral treatments. The main aim of this study is to assess the effects of the light thinning, the shrub clearing, the sowing of leguminous plants and the grazing, on the mineral nutrition and the growth of the cork-oaks. Our hypothesis is that such a management could also have a positive effect on the whole functioning of the forest system due to the suppression of the competition for water and nutrients and to the presence of animals. Works already undertaken in the area of agroforestry are scarce and the authors who worked on the forest management effects on tree mineral nutrition and/or growth are scarcer (KENNEDY, 1981, COLE *et al.*, 1995, ORGEAS & BONIN, 1996, ROBERT *et al.*, 1996 b). A few other studies were dedicated to the effects of intercropping of leguminous plants (HAINES, HAINES & WHITE, 1978, SCHÖNAU & HERBERT, 1983, NAMBIAR & NETHERCOTT, 1987) but they mainly concerned young tree plantations. More often than not, the closest works dealt with the effects of the forest plantations fertilization (MILLER & MILLER, 1976, CAMIRE & BERNIER, 1981) or with the comparison of sites of unequal edaphic quality (ERDMANN, 1988). All these studies, that used a more or less common methodology, showed that changes in the availability of soil nutrients to plant (due to forest management or to fertilization) found expression in the mineral composition (increase of N, P, Ca contents, decrease of Mn contents) of the treated tree leaves (CAMIRE & BERNIER, 1981, ROBERT *et al.*, 1996b) and/or in the growth rate (KENNEDY, 1981). As far as the forest evergreen species were concerned, studies on the mineral nutrition focused especially on the utilization of nutrients by the evergreen species or the retranslocation of the nutrients (CHAPIN *et al.* 1980, GRAY & SCHLESINGER, 1981, DEL ARCO *et al.*, 1991, ESCUDERO *et al.*, 1992, PUGNAIRE & CHAPIN 1993,

KARLSSON, 1994) and their adaptation to poor soils because of their high nutrient efficiency (MILLER *et al.*, 1979).

The objective of this work, is the assessment of the effects of some sylvopastoral treatments on cork-oak growth and mineral nutrition. To this aim, the foliar and soil analyses and the radial and longitudinal growth measurements in the control plots and in the treated ones are compared. Then, for the Catalan sites, the study of the relations between the mineral nutrition data and the longitudinal growth tries to make a better understanding of cork-oak physiology, providing a supplementary example to the study of the mineral nutrition of the evergreen trees which current studies are still much debated. Results are discussed in order to assess the profit for these trees of such sylvopastoral treatments with regard to the whole functioning of the cork-oak forest system.

METHODS

* Experimental sites

The study was conducted on eight sites scattered in the Catalonian region (North-East of Spain, 41°54' N 3°08' E and South of France, 42°30' N 3° E) and in Sardinia (Italy, 40°N 3°E). Four of the Catalan sites are located in the oriental Pyrenean range at an altitude from 100 m to 400 m. The tree level is mainly formed by the cork-oak (*Quercus suber* L.) and the understorey vegetation by a typical Mediterranean shrub-oak forest : *Erica arborea* L., *Arbutus unedo* L., *Pistacia lentiscus* L., *Cistus monpellierensis* L., *Ulex parviflorus* Pourr., *Lonicera implexa* Ait., *Calycotome spinosa* Link., *Lavandula stoechas* L.. The fifth site, situated in the Catalonian Littoral Range, at an altitude of about 150 m, is a more thermophile site : presence of *Pinus halepensis* Mill., *Pistacia lentiscus* L. and *Rosmarinus officinalis* L.. Two of the three Sardinian sites (ranging from 470 to 600 m) are located in the North of the island and one in the centre. Here, we noticed more humid tendencies than in the Catalan sites because of the presence of *Quercus pubescens* Willd., *Cistus salvaefolius* L. and *Cytisus villosus* Pourret.

Table 1 : Soil characteristics of the 14 Catalan cork-oak plots. Values are the mean $\pm$ standard deviation.

	Gravel & Stones, %	Clay, %	Silt, %	Sand, %	pH Water	O.M., g/kg	C/N
Depth 0-30 cm	28 $\pm$ 11	14 $\pm$ 4	35 $\pm$ 6	51 $\pm$ 10	5.5 $\pm$ 0.6	42 $\pm$ 13	15 $\pm$ 3

	N	P	K	Ca	Mg	CEC, cmol/kg
	g/kg					
Depth 0-30 cm	1.64 $\pm$ 0.60	0.044 $\pm$ 0.027	0.13 $\pm$ 0.08	1.17 $\pm$ 0.62	0.20 $\pm$ 0.09	11 $\pm$ 2

-Climate

During the three years of study, the climate was a typical Sub-humid Mediterranean climate, according to the Emberger classification, with dry summer (8 mm to 62 mm in July and August) and mild winter (4.3°C to 6.6°C, minimum temperature in January). Depending on the sites, the annual rainfall varied from 700 mm in Sardinia to 1000 mm in Catalunya.

-Soils

The **Table 1** shows the main characteristics of the Catalan plots soils. These slightly acid (pH range from 4.5 to 6.3) soils are relatively shallow (~ 30 cm) and are generally located on a primary bedrock (granite, schists or gneiss). The humus can be identified as an acid mull or a moder. The soil profiles can be described as AC type, although in most of the plots, there was a beginning of a formation of a B horizon, differing from the A horizon by the brown colour and the structure. For these reasons, these soils can be classified, following the French classification, as an intermediate between the rankers and the brown acid soils. They range from a sand-silt texture to a silt-sand texture and although the CEC is not bad, they are poor in available mineral nutrients like N, P, K, Ca, Mg, which can be explained by the sandy granulometry and the lack of clay. The values of the C/N ratio, which can reach 20 in some control plots, are relatively high in the whole sites because the litter is slow in decomposing. They represent the typical sandy acid soils, poor in gravel and stones, which the cork-oak is used to spread (although too shallow).

-Sylvopastoral treatments

The considered sites consist each one of three 400 m² plots : a control plot (CO) and two treated plots, except for one Catalan site which consists of only two plots, the control and CG ones. The treatments are a mechanical light thinning and a shrub clearing (C), followed in the CG plot by sowing of well-adapted leguminous plants (*Trifolium subterraneum* L., MASSON *et al.*, 1991) and grasses (*Dactylis glomerata* L., *Festuca arundinacea* Schreber). The CG plots are grazed by various animals depending on the site (goats, sheep, horses or cow cattle) and the installation of herbaceous plants was favoured by the application of fertilizer (N : between 50 and 60 kg/ha, P₂O₅ : between 50 and 80 kg/ha). On the Sardinian

sites and in one Catalan site, the C plots were submitted only to a manual shrub clearing without thinning, followed by the grazing. For these sites, the CG plots were not sown and fertilized, and the herbaceous plants level consists of spontaneous leguminous plants and grasses. We consider that the fertilization which was applied for the establishment of the grasses had no effect on the trees because of the passage of time between the application and the sampling (two or three years, depending on the sites) and because of the relatively light application rates.

-Planting characteristics

The tree density is higher in the control plots with an average (mean of the basal areas of seven sites $\pm$ standard deviation) of 30 ± 9 m²/ha. In the treated plots, the thinning led to a lower density : the C plots mean basal area is 28 ± 12 m²/ha and the CG plots one is 23 ± 7 m²/ha. The average height of the trees is similar in all the plots : 7 ± 1.5 m for the Control plots, 7.2 ± 2.2 m for the C plots and 7.7 ± 1.6 m for the CG plots.

*** Measurements and analysis**

In each 400 m² plot, 10 representative trees of the stand and following the distribution of the diameter classes were chosen for the study. These trees were studied for 3 years (1992, 1993, 1994).

-Foliar sampling

Twice a year (February and June), four branches were collected in four directions on the mid crown of the ten trees of each plot in each eight sites. The age of the leaves which were sampled could not be determined exactly but the leaves which were sampled in February were between 8 and 10 months old and the ones which were sampled in June between 10 and 14 months old. The reasons for sampling these leaves are detailed in ROBERT *et al.*, 1996b; the vegetative rest period is the sampling period which is recommended by GUHA and MITCHELL, 1965 and BONNEAU, 1988 and the same leaf class is sampled in February and in June. The leaves were sorted out in the laboratory in order to make one sample a plot. These leaves were dried (70 °C) and ground before chemical analysis.

-Chemical analysis

- Leaves

Total nitrogen was determined after digestion in H₂SO₄ in the presence of H₂O₂ (LINDNER & HARLEY, 1942). The other elements were determined after extraction of the ashes obtained at 550 °C with HCl. Nitrogen and phosphorus were determined spectrophotometrically using indophenol blue and the phosphomolybdic complex, respectively. The other elements were determined by emission (K) or atomic absorption spectrophotometry (Ca, Mg, Cu, Fe, Mn, Zn).

- Soils

Soil samples were collected in winter (February), in the five Catalan sites only. Particle size determinations and chemical analyses (organic carbon, Kjeldahl nitrogen, Dyer phosphorus, CEC) were carried out using standard methods.

-Growth

The longitudinal growth measurements were made in June 1991 and in June 1993 on the branches collected for chemical analysis. On these branches, the two last flushes delimited by the scars were measured (CARITAT *et al.*, 1994). In June 1993, the measurements concerned the two last flushes (LG92 and LG93) which correspond to the growth of 1992 and 1993 respectively. The radial growth of the wood of each selected tree was assessed by measuring the four last rings (four years preceding the collection) of small wood cylinders extracted from the trunk with the Pressler borer.

RESULTS

*** Effects of sylvopastoral treatments**

The differences in growth or in foliar mineral contents were tested using the analysis of variance considering the eight sites as blocks. When the analyses concerned successive dates on the same plots (i.e. when the data were not independent), a split-plot design was used : each plot associated to a date was considered as a subplot.

Table 2 : Effects of the sylvopastoral treatments on cork-oak growth (CO: control; C: cleared; CG: cleared, sown and grazed).

	CO	C	CG	Signification
Longitudinal Growth (cm)				
1991	2.89 b	3.14 b	4.08 a	*
Catalan sites				
1992	3.09 b	3.74 a	3.95 a	**
Catalan sites				
1993				
Sardinian & Catalan sites	2.78	3.01	3.18	N.S. (P=0.053)
Radial Growth (sum of the 4 last rings, mm)				
1989-1992				
Sardinian & Catalan sites	6.65	6.59	7.11	N.S.

Unilateral test (* : $P \leq 0.05$, ** : $P \leq 0.01$); N.S. : non-significant.

Table 3 : Effects of the treatments on the foliar nutrient contents (6 sites: 4 Catalan and 2 Sardinian, 3 years, split-plot design) in June of 1992, 1993 and 1994.

	CO	C	CG	SIGNIFICATION
Nutrients				
% d.m.				
N	1.33 b	1.41 ab	1.48 a	*
P	0.10 b	0.12 a	0.13 a	*
K	0.63	0.59	0.61	N.S.
Ca	0.80	0.82	0.80	N.S.
Mg	0.16	0.16	0.16	N.S.
ppm d.m.				
Cu	6.2	6.4	6.4	N.S.
Zn	20	22	22	N.S.
Fe	177	175	172	N.S.
Mn	1086	863	969	N.S.

Unilateral test (* : $P \leq 0.05$) N.S. : non significant

- Effects on growth

The sylvopastoral treatments did not have any effect on the radial growth, but increased the longitudinal growth, which was significantly higher on the CG plots than on the control plots CO, (Table 2). The effects seemed to be additive : the shrub clearing and the thinning induced a first increase (not always significant) and the sowing of the leguminous plants and the grazing added a supplementary effect which led, in the CG plot, to an increase of 12 to 30 % of the length of the flushes.

- Effect on leaf mineral composition

The main registered effect was the significant increase of N and P leaf contents on the treated plots compared to those of the control (Table 3). Each treatment resulted in an increase in the N leaf content, just like the one we observed for longitudinal growth. The effect of the shrub clearing (C plot, increase of 5 % of N leaf content) was of the same range as of the sowing and the grazing (CG plot, increase of 6 % of N leaf content). On the other hand, the effect on P leaf content was different : the main improvement was due to the shrub clearing (increase of 20 % of the leaf P content). The sowing and the grazing did not have any supplementary effect on the leaf P content.

Concerning the other macronutrients (K, Ca, Mg) and the micronutrients (Cu, Zn, Fe, Mn), no change in the leaf contents from one plot to another was observed. The non significance of the difference between Mn leaf contents in the control (CO : 1086 ppm) and in the treated plots (C: 863 ppm, CG : 969 ppm) was related to the difference of the responses observed in Sardinia and in Catalonia. Indeed, the steady decrease of the Mn leaf contents observed in the four cleared Catalan sites (C) did not exist in the Sardinian ones (Table 4).

- Effect on soil parameters

As expected and in relation to the short duration of the experiment, three to four years after the beginning of the treatments, the differences between the soil mineral compositions were not significant. As we can see in the Table 5, the effect of the shrub clearing (C) alone was very low. In accordance with the trend towards an increase of the organic matter in the CG plot, provided by the grazing and the shrub clearing, a decrease of the C/N ratio

Table 4 : Comparison between the effects of the C treatment on Mn foliar contents in the Catalan sites and in the Sardinian sites in February and June 1994 and over the three years period.

	Catalan sites (n=4)			Sardinian sites (n=3)		
	Mn foliar contents, ppm d.m.					
	CO	C	Signification	CO	C	Signification
Feb 94	870 a	623 b	*	860	1217	N.S.
Jun 94	895 a	660 b	*	867	883	N.S.
Three years period	1112	763	N.S. P=0.056	817	925	N.S.

(* : $P \leq 0.05$) N.S. : non-significant

Table 5: Effects of the sylvopastoral treatment on the soil parameters. Values are the mean $\pm$ Standard deviation of the five Catalan sites.

	CO	C	CG	Signification
N, g/kg	1.50 $\pm$ 0.45	1.40 $\pm$ 0.43	1.96 $\pm$ 0.62	$P_{C/CG}=0.062$
P ₂ O ₅ , g/kg	0.043 $\pm$ 0.022	0.049 $\pm$ 0.029	0.052 $\pm$ 0.030	N.S.
K, g/kg	0.115 $\pm$ 0.048	0.108 $\pm$ 0.067	0.165 $\pm$ 0.095	N.S.
Ca, g/kg	1.03 $\pm$ 0.54	1.05 $\pm$ 0.65	1.34 $\pm$ 0.54	N.S.
Mg, g/kg	0.170 $\pm$ 0.072	0.177 $\pm$ 0.086	0.235 $\pm$ 0.075	N.S.
pH (water)	5.28 $\pm$ 0.32	5.46 $\pm$ 0.73	5.56 $\pm$ 0.45	N.S.
CEC, meq/kg	11.0 $\pm$ 1.79	10.7b $\pm$ 1.59	11.4a $\pm$ 2.05	*
C, g/kg	23.2 $\pm$ 5.89	20.5 $\pm$ 4.30	27.7 $\pm$ 9.50	N.S.
O.M., g/kg	40.0 $\pm$ 10.1	35.3 $\pm$ 7.40	47.6 $\pm$ 16.3	N.S.
C/N	16.2 $\pm$ 2.55	15.8 $\pm$ 3.42	13.0 $\pm$ 1.72	$P_{CO/CG}=0.059$

Unilateral test (* : $P \leq 0.05$) N.S. : non-significant

($P=0.059$), the significant increase of the CEC and the trends towards an increase of N ($P=0.062$), P, K, Ca, and Mg soil contents from the C plot to the CG plot suggest a better mineralisation of the organic matter in the CG plot.

*** Main features of the cork-oak mineral nutrition**

The whole data collected (soil and foliar analysis, longitudinal growth) during the two years of 1992 and 1993 in the fourteen Catalan plots (two or three plots in each of the five sites) were gathered together to allow the study of the relations between the cork-oak longitudinal growth and its mineral nutrition considering a wide range of values.

Table 6 shows the high positive correlation between the longitudinal growth and the soil parameters especially with the pH and the Ca soil content (Fig. 1) and with K, P, N, Mg soil contents, the CEC and the organic matter rate. All these parameters can be considered as indicators of the soil fertility. Inversely, indicators of soil acidity such as Fe, Mn or Al contents were slightly but negatively correlated to the longitudinal growth. These results suggest a general trend towards a better cork-oak longitudinal growth on the least acidic and most fertile soils. The observed correlations between the longitudinal growth and the foliar analyses confirmed these results except for N (Table 7). On the whole of the sites, there was a positive correlation between the longitudinal growth and the P and Ca leaf contents. The significance of the positive correlation with K and the negative one with Mn leaf content (which may express its toxicity) varied depending on the date. In spite of the lack of knowledge about the toxicity of the Mn on the cork-oak longitudinal growth, the high positive correlation between these contents and the Mn soil ones ($r=0.871^{***}$, Figure 2) shows that the high Mn leaf contents which were observed depend on the Mn soil contents.

DISCUSSION

*** Effects of sylvopastoral treatments**

The results obtained concerning the radial growth have not shown any significant effect of the sylvopastoral treatments. The age of the trees (80-150 years old) could explain this apparent absence of effect : a longer period of treatment may be necessary to observe the effects on the radial growth. The effect of the treatments seems to be concentrated on the

Table 6: Main relations between the soil parameters and the longitudinal growth in 1992 and in 1993, respectively LG92 and LG93 (n=14).

	LG92	pH (KCl)	O.M.	N	P	K	Ca	Mg	CEC	Fe	Mn	Al
LG92	-	+0.803 ***	+0.514 *	+0.589 *	+0.747 ***	+0.625 **	+0.841 ***	+0.557 *	+0.524 *	-0.502 *	-0.311	-0.449
LG93	+0.741 ***	+0.664 **	+0.573 *	+0.618 *	+0.337	+0.731 **	+0.605 *	+0.257	+0.602 *	-0.481	+0.095	-0.155

(* : $P \leq 0.05$, ** : $P \leq 0.01$, *** : $P \leq 0.001$); N.S. : non-significant.

Figure 1 : Correlation between the soil Ca content and the longitudinal growth of 1992 (LG92)

longitudinal growth which is more likely to react to a change in the soil fertility than the radial growth, and can be interpreted as a consequence of the N and P effects. In the CG plot, the increase in N leaf content can be explained by the suppression of the competition with the understorey vegetation for the N available in the soil and by the combined effect of the leguminous plants and grazing. Indeed, the effect of the N-fixing plants on the increase of the N foliar concentration and on the growth of the trees has already been reported for *Trifolium subterraneum*, with the Sycamore tree, (HAINES *et al.*, 1978) and for *Lupinus angustifolius*, with *Pinus radiata*, (NAMBIAR *et al.*, 1987). The effect of the grazing has been reported too by ESCUDERO *et al.*, (1985) for *Quercus rotundifolia* in the Spanish "dehesa" and was explained by the contribution of the grazing to the decrease of the turn over time of the organic matter of the soil, compared with other tree ecosystems. In this study, although the turn over time of the organic matter was not assessed, the trend towards the increase of the N soil contents and the decrease of the C/N ratio in the CG plots are in accordance with this hypothesis. The light leaf P content increase which was observed in the C and CG plots suggests a better P nutrition. A soil P enrichment due to the increase of the organic matter provided by the shrub clearing cannot be excluded, but it was not supported by the differences observed in the P soil contents. The leaf P effect was thus attributed to the reduction of the competition between the trees after the shrub clearing and the thinning. However, considering the limited information available about this subject, further work is needed.

The high foliar Mn contents may be a special feature of the evergreen trees and/or the acid soil-spreading species. Previous works (ROBERT *et al.*, 1996a and 1996b) on cork-oak showed the high Mn foliar contents as it has been reported too for *Quercus ilex* (CARITAT *et al.*, 1990) and for some French douglas firs (DUCHAUFOR, 1988). The trend towards the decrease in the leaf Mn contents, in treated plots in Catalonia, has already been reported in a previous study (ROBERT *et al.*, 1996b) and is in agreement with the observations made by CAMIRE & BERNIER (1981) 2 and 3 years after N application on pine plantations. Moreover, SCHÖNAU & HERBERT (1983) showed that the highest Mn foliar contents for

Table 7: Correlations between N, P, K, Mg, Ca and Mn leaf contents and the longitudinal growth in 1992 and in 1993, respectively LG92 and LG93.

LG92	N	P	K	Ca	Mg	Mn
February 93	-0.081	+0.432	+0.672**	+0.677**	+0.036	-0.507*
June 93	+0.153	+0.549*	+0.373	+0.541*	-0.085	-0.458

LG93	N	P	K	Ca	Mg	Mn
February 93	-0.288	+0.504*	+0.279	+0.896***	-0.501*	-0.091
June 93	+0.019	+0.733**	+0.328	+0.534*	-0.535*	-0.028

(* = P < 0.05, ** = P < 0.01, *** = P < 0.001); n=14.

Figure 2: Correlation between the soil Mn content and the leaf Mn content in June 1993.

Eucalyptus grandis occurred generally under the least favourable growing conditions. This trend was not observed in Sardinian plots and the reasons for this difference are not known yet.

*** Features of the cork-oak longitudinal growth and mineral nutrition**

The longitudinal growth of these cork-oaks seemed to be higher in the least acid and the most fertile soils. The good relation between the longitudinal growth and the Ca soil contents (Fig. 1) may reflect the importance of this nutrient in the cork-oak mineral biomass (LEONARDI *et al.*, 1992) and could be considered as a good indicator of the fertility of these slightly acid soils : the higher pH, CEC and organic matter rate in the most fertile soils would lead to a higher soil Ca content. Similar relations between the longitudinal growth and the leaf nutrients contents were observed (although not always significant), except for N leaf contents which was not correlated to the longitudinal growth. The Nitrogen retranslocation towards the youngest leaves and the storage organs (trunk and roots) which is an important process in the mineral nutrition of the evergreen species (MILLER, 1984) and thus in the cork-oak (LEONARDI *et al.*, 1992, ROBERT *et al.*, 1996b) may have obscured the relations between the N leaf contents and the longitudinal growth (the leaves collected were relatively old : 8-10-month old in February). Although the negative correlation between the leaf Mn content and the longitudinal growth was not steadily demonstrated, it would be interesting to dedicate further work on this subject.

Finally, the sylvopastoral treatments applied in the North-Mediterranean forests in order to reduce the fire risks and for the improvement of the cork exploitation, seem to be also favourable to the cork-oak N and P nutrition and the longitudinal growth. The greatest effect on mineral nutrition has been observed in the thinned, cleared, sown and grazed plot. The positive action of these kind of treatments on the whole system soil-grasses-trees with reciprocal benefit is in agreement with the observations made on other agrosylvopastoral systems, for example in the spanish "dehesa" (JOFFRE *et al.*, 1988). As the bark may contain up to 29 % of the nitrogen of the cork-oak trunk and branches (LEONARDI *et al.*, 1992), the N nutrition improvement may also have a positive effect on the cork production as suggested by ORGEAS *et al.* (1996).